

Concurrent Multi-Scale Design Optimization of Composite Frame Structure with Specific Manufacturing Constraints

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Abstract This paper presents a gradient based concurrent multi-scale design optimization method for composite frame structure with considering specific manufacturing constraints representative of the actual industrial requirements. The components of geometrical parameter of the frame in the macro-structural scale and discrete fiber winding angle in the micro-material scale are introduced as the independent design variables in the two geometrical scales through the DMO (Discrete Material Optimization) approach to realize the simultaneous optimization of macroscopic topology and microscopic material selection. The specific manufacturing constraints are explicitly included in the optimization problem/scheme as series of linear inequalities or equalities mathematical expressions with respect to the microscopic candidate artificial material density. The linear constraints and optimization problems are solved by Sequential Linear Programming (SLP) optimization algorithm with move limit strategy. The capabilities of the proposed method are demonstrated on compliance minimization, subject to constraint on the composite structure volume. Numerical results for different scales (single macro- or micro-scale and concurrent multi-scale), with considering or not considering specific manufacturing constraints optimization models of an academic ten-beam composite frame structure are presented. Different optimization models represent the potential to achieve ultra-light design of composite frame structure for different levels of lightweight design.

Keywords Concurrent multi-scale optimization · Composite frame structure · Design guidelines · Manufacturing constraints

1 Introduction

Laminated composites frame structure like glass or carbon fiber-reinforced polymers (GFRP/CFRP) have been extensively used in aerospace structure and civil engineering with excellent mechanical properties and performances for the expected ultra-light and stiffness structures. Especially for aerospace vehicles, main load-bearing structure of satellite, spatial station, transmission tower and wind turbines structure, et al. where large-scale, high stiffness and low weight are emphasized. Therefore, laminated composites optimization has undergone tremendous development in last decades. Most contributions on this topic have been summarized in the review article of Ghiasi et al. (2009, 2010)^[1, 2] and Bakis et al. (2002)^[3]. It is worth

noting/necessary to mention that, in recent years, discrete fiber material optimization of laminated composites has achieved considerable progress and attracted much attention. Based on an extension of the multi-phase topology optimization (Sigmund and Torquato 1997^[4]), Lund and co-author (Lund and Stegmann 2005^[5]; Stegmann and Lund 2005^[6]) proposed a novel idea for multi-phase optimization of laminated composites, the DMO method has been successfully used to dispose many physical problem (Hvejsel et al. 2011^[7]; Lund 2009^[8]; Niu et al. 2010^[9]; Duan et al. 2014^[10]). As an alternative to the DMO schemes, Bruyneel (2011)^[11] introduced the Shape Functions with Penalization (SFP) scheme based on the shape functions of a quadrangular first order finite element and later the method was extended to also include three and eight node elements, see Bruyneel et al. (2011)^[12]. Gao et al. (2012)^[13] proposed a so-called Bi-valued Coding Parameterization (BCP) scheme which distinguishes itself from SFP schemes in that it does not have a limit on the number of applied material candidates and have a relatively higher efficiency.

Despite remarkable achievements have been made for microscopic laminated composites design and optimization, there still have **two challenging issues** for laminated composites optimization. **The first one** is designed for real, that means a certain design guidelines or rules, referred to as manufacturing constraints should be sufficiently considered to mitigate the adverse effects of the laminated composites material's weaknesses. In Bailie et al. (1997)^[14], they mentioned eight weaknesses associated with composite laminates, and an efficient way to prevent these weakness from happening is to follow a set of fundamental manufacturing constraints based on industry past experience from test and analysis. In the early days, Costin and Wang (1992, 1993)^[15, 16] considered manufacturing constraints in aircraft structure design with physical and shape function as design variables. Manne and Tsai (1998)^[17] utilized plydrop tapering for thickness optimization of symmetric layups to avoid warping. And recently, adopted SFP interpolation scheme, Bruyneel et al. (2012)^[18] realized the optimal stacking sequence design of laminates composite with considering several manufacturing constraints. Irisarri et al. (2014)^[19] considered an extensive set of design guidelines to realize the optimal design of laminated composite structures with ply drops used stacking sequence table (SST) method. Sørensen and Lund (2013)^[20], Sørensen et al. (2014)^[21] carried out the serial works on thickness design of laminate composite with certain manufacturing constraints.

Another challenging issue is how to satisfy the urgent and harsh requirements for the ultra-light and complicated structure in practical applications especially in aerospace engineering. As we know, laminated composites material is a structural material, the fibers are usually stacked in a number of layers and bonded together by a resin, so the stacking sequence/ply parameters (fiber

orientation, fiber content and layer thickness) strongly impact the material properties, which offer/give a good opportunity to tailor the material and excavate the potential and advantages of the laminated composites. Hence, only single-scale (macro-structural or micro-material) optimization of laminated composites is not competent to realize the ultra-light design of laminated composites, how to further excavate the potential and advantages of the laminated composites from two geometrical scales (macro-structural and micro-material), sequentially, consider the coupling effect of macro- and micro-scale design variables, has become a challenging problem for optimization method and theory.

So combine with the multi-scale optimization theory and adequately consider the coupling effecting of macro-structural and micro-material, the present paper proposed a novel method to investigate the concurrent multi-scale optimization of composite frame with respect to minimum structural compliance under volume constraint with specific manufacturing constraints.

2. Concurrent multi-scale optimal design of composite frame adopting Discrete Material Optimization (DMO) approach

2.1 Concurrent optimization of composite frame

Because in most aerospace applications, the frame structure frequently adopt constant circle cross-section, so in the present paper, for easy of deduction and no loss of generality, the constant circle cross-section tube was investigated. In macroscopic, the radius of cross-section is recognized as the macro design variable (r_i), similar as in classical frame structure topology optimization, the tube's radius can be recognized as size and topology variables at the same time. When the radius reaches its lower limit, the tube can be regarded to be deleted from the ground structure to realize the structural topology optimization (Bendsøe and Sigmund^[22], Eschenauer and Olhoff^[23], Topping^[24]). As has been shown in the schematic diagram of Fig. 1, the middle hidden line is the macro design variable has reached the lower limit.

Fig. 1 Schematic diagram of the concurrent optimization of composite frame

In microscopic, the discrete fiber winding angles selection is solved by using the so-called

DMO approach in the sense that the structural constituents are chosen from among a given set of candidate materials. In most practical applications, the candidate materials are restricted to $[0^\circ, \mp 45^\circ, 90^\circ]$ plies, which are the conventional orientations used in aeronautics (Baker et al. 2004^[25]) considering the cost requirement of manufacturing.

2.2 Discrete Material Optimization (DMO) approach

The discrete material optimization formulation is encompassed in the same parameterization and can be solved in the finite element framework. In DMO approach, The elemental constitutive matrix $\mathbf{D}_{i,j}^e$ (the superscript e refers to “element”, and the subscripts mean the i 'th tube and j 'th layer) per layer can be expressed as a weighted sum of the candidate materials, which is characterized by a constitutive matrix $\mathbf{D}_{i,j,c}$. In general, for multi-layer structures, the interpolation method must be implemented layer-wise for each element, i.e., for all layers in all elements. And there are various parameterization schemes have been developed in Lund and Stegmann 2005^[5]; Stegmann and Lund 2005^[6]. Consequently, the interpolation scheme is written by layers, and the constitutive relation for the j -th layer can be expressed as a sum over the element number of candidate materials:

$$\mathbf{D}_{i,j}^e = \sum_{c=1}^{N^{\text{cand}}} \omega_{i,j,c} \mathbf{D}_{i,j,c} \quad (1)$$

where each candidate material is characterized by a constitutive matrix $\mathbf{D}_{i,j,c}$. The weighting functions $\omega_{i,j,c}$ (the subscripts present the i 'th tube, j 'th layer and c 'th candidate material) must all attain values between 0 and 1 because no matrix can contribute more than the physical material properties, and a negative contribution is physically meaningless. In Eq. (1), the parameterization model is realized single-layers and layer-wise for multiple layers for a large number of candidate materials. The weighting functions can be expressed as

$$\omega_{i,j,c} = x_{i,j,c}^p \quad (2)$$

3 Manufacturing constraints

Recently years, manufacturing constraints problems have attracted much attention in laminate composite design, e.g., Minimum percentage of each orientation constraint (10% rule), contiguity constraint, balance constraint, symmetry constraint, see, e.g., Bruyneel et al. 2012^[18] Seresta et al. (2007)^[26], Kassapoglou (2010)^[27], Zein et al. (2012)^[28], Kennedy and Martins (2013)^[29], and Irisarri et al. 2014^[19]; Damtol constraint, ply-drop design constraint see, e.g., Irisarri et al. 2014^[19]; Thickness variation rate and intermediate constraint see, e.g., Sørensen and Lund 2013^[20], Sørensen et al. 2014^[21]. Taking into account the relevance of the above mentioned

manufacturing constraints with composite frame structure, the variable stiffness design i.e., thickness variation and ply-drop problems are not considering in this work, which will be left for future work to research.

3.1 Contiguity constraint (CC)

Contiguity constraint i.e., CC, the definition of the contiguity constraint is no more than a given number of plies of the same orientation should be stacked together, the maximum contiguity layers limit is set here noted as CL . More specifically description, the constraints on contiguity impose a limit on the maximum allowable number of contiguous identical Unidirectional (UD) fiber material candidates to avoid e.g. matrix cracking failure (Sørensen et al. 2014^[21]). The contiguity constraint with respect to micro-scale parameter can be formulated as linear inequality as Eq. (3). Let $CL \in \mathbb{N}$ denote the contiguity limit, for any $i \in N^{\text{tub}}$, $j \in N^{\text{lay}}$, $c \in N^{\text{cand}}$ it should follow the Eq. (3), and the loop should meet the dimension of $j + CL \leq N^{\text{lay}}$. Where, N^{tub} is the number of tubes in the frame structure. N^{can} is the number of candidate materials in each layer. N^{lay} is the number of layers in each tube, and in this paper the number of layers i.e., N^{lay} is assumed as the same in each tube.

$$\sum_{j=1}^{N^{\text{lay}}} x_{i,j,c} + \dots + x_{i,j+CL,c} \leq CL \quad \forall (i, c \in 1, 2, \dots, N^{\text{cand}}), j + CL \leq N^{\text{lay}} \quad (\text{Contiguity constraint i.e. CC}) \quad (3)$$

3.2 10% rule (Ten Percent Rule, TPR)

10% rule i.e. TPR, a minimum of the 10% of plies in each of the 0° , $\pm 45^\circ$ and 90° direction is required. It is important to note that the 10% fiber-dominated guideline is often interpreted differently with regard to the $\pm 45^\circ$ plies. Some project directives require there be least 10% $+45^\circ$ and 10% -45° plies, rather than 5% of $+45^\circ$ and -45° plies. There are no guidelines that establish a rigorous differentiation between these two alternative minimum 45° ply contents. Other projects have issued guidelines requiring at least 6% (rather than 10%) 90° plies provided there are at least 20% $\pm 45^\circ$ plies.

$$\sum_{j=1}^{N^{\text{lay}}} x_{i,j,c} \geq 10\% N^{\text{lay}} \quad \forall (i, c \in [0^\circ, \pm 45^\circ, 90^\circ]) \quad (10\% \text{ rule i.e. MC2}) \quad (4)$$

3.3 Balance constraint (BC)

Balance constraint i.e. BC, this constraint means that angle plies (those at any angle other than 0° and 90°) should occur only in balanced pairs, with the same number of $+\theta^\circ$ and $-\theta^\circ$ plies ($\theta^\circ \neq 0^\circ, 90^\circ$). For the set of the $0^\circ, \mp 45^\circ, 90^\circ$ candidate materials, any $+45^\circ$ ply should be accompanied by a -45° ply. A typical example of the difference between balanced and

unbalanced symmetric laminates is shown in Fig. 2, and the parameterized equality linear constraint with respect to candidate artificial material density, i.e. $x_{i,j,c}$ can be expressed as Eq. (5)

Fig. 2 Illustration of balanced and unbalanced symmetric laminates^[14]

$$\sum_{j=1}^{N^{lay}} x_{i,j,+c} - \sum_{j=1}^{N^{lay}} x_{i,j,-c} = 0 \quad \forall (i, j, c \neq (0^\circ \cup 90^\circ)) \quad (\text{Balance constraint i.e. MC4}) \quad (5)$$

3.4 DamTol constraint (DTC)

DamTol constraint i.e. DTC, no 0° ply should be placed on the lower and upper surface of the laminate, this manufacturing constraint is very reasonable for composite frame structure, because it is not easy to wind the fiber on the lower and upper surface of the tube with 0° fiber i.e., fiber winding angle along the axial, and such winding is easy delamination. This constraint can be express as the artificial density of 0° candidate material in the upper surface is zero and the same as lower surface i.e. $x_{i,1,c} = 0 \quad \forall (i, c \in [0^\circ])$, $x_{i,N^{lay},c} = 0 \quad \forall (i, c \in [0^\circ])$. The separate two equality constraints can be compounded as one equality constraint as Eq. (6)

$$x_{i,1,c} + x_{i,N^{lay},c} = 0 \quad \forall (i, c \in [0^\circ]) \quad (\text{Damtol i.e. MC3}) \quad (6)$$

3.5 Symmetry constraint (SC)

Symmetry constraint i.e. SC, whenever possible, winding sequence should be symmetric about the mid-plane. There are two reasons why this guideline is representative of good practice: (1) to uncouple bending and membrane response, and (2) to prevent warping under thermal loading. Clearly, this guideline can not always be rigorously enforced such as in zones where thickness is tapered. However, any asymmetry existing due to manufacturing constraints should be minimized.

$$t_{i,j} = t_{i,N^{lay}-j+1} \quad \forall i, j \in [1, N^{lay}] \quad (7a)$$

$$x_{i,j,+c} = x_{i,N^{lay}-j+1,+c} \quad \forall (i, c \in [0^\circ, \pm 45^\circ, 90^\circ]), j \in [1, N^{lay}] \quad (7b)$$

3.6 DMO normalization constraint (DMOnC)

DMO normalization constraint i.e. DMOnC, as has mentioned, in order to keep the physically meaning in the case of a mass constraint or eigenfrequency optimization, the sum of the candidate artificial materials density in the same layer should equal to one, which should be realized layer-wise for multiple layers laminate composite.

$$\sum_{c=1}^{N^{can}} x_{i,j,c} = 1 \quad \forall (i, j) \quad (\text{DMO normalization constraint i.e. DMOnc}) \quad (8)$$

4 Mathematical formulation of the optimization problem and the structure analysis model

4.1 Mathematical formulation of the optimization problem

We consider the concurrent multi-scale optimization of composite frame structure with the objective of minimizing the structure compliance under specific manufacturing and total volume constraints. The detail of the specific manufacturing constraints has been presented in Section 3. The micro-scale discrete fiber winding angle ($x_{i,j,c}$) and macro-scale tube's inner radius (r_i) of circle cross-section are introduced as the independent design variables to realize the topology and stacking sequences optimization on the two geometrical scales, simultaneously. Considering symmetry constraint, the optimization formulation can be listed as follows:

$$\text{Find } \mathbf{X} = \{r_i, x_{i,j,c}\} \quad i \in N^{tub}, j \in N^{lay}/2, c \in N^{cand} \quad (9a)$$

$$\text{Min } \mathbf{C} = \mathbf{U}^T \mathbf{K} \mathbf{U} \quad (9b)$$

$$\text{S.T } \mathbf{K}(\mathcal{D}_n^e(r_i, x_{i,j,c})) \mathbf{U} = \mathbf{F} \quad (9c)$$

$$V(r_i) = \sum_{i=1}^{N^{tub}} \pi [t_{tot}^i{}^2 + 2r_i t_{tot}^i] L_i \leq \bar{V} \quad (\text{Volume constraint i.e. VC}) \quad (9d)$$

$$\text{MC'S (CC, TPR, BC, DTC, SC, DMOnc)} \quad (9e)$$

$$r_i \in [r_{min}, 0.1] \quad \forall i \quad (9f)$$

$$x_{i,j,c} \in [0, 1] \quad \forall (i, j, c) \quad (9g)$$

6 Numerical examples

In the present section, the classical ten-beams composite frames structure as isotropic frame structure had been investigate in many research and here be considered as an academic example, the loading/boundary conditions and geometric sizes with tubes number are shown in Fig. 3. Considering the engineering practical application, we assume every composite tube has the same number of layers i.e., $N^{lay} = 20$, and every layer has a constant thickness i.e., $t_{tot}^i/N^{lay} = 0.1mm$.

Fig. 3 Ten tubes of composites frame structure

The fiber candidate materials are glass fiber reinforced epoxy with the orthotropic properties as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 General material properties of a type of uni-directional carbon reinforced epoxy

E_{11}	143 GPa
$E_{22} = E_{33}$	10 GPa
G_{12}	6 GPa
G_{13}	5 GPa
G_{23}	3 GPa
ν_{12}	0.3
ν_{13}	0.2
ν_{23}	0.52
ρ	1800 kg/m ³

In order to clearly demonstrate the optimization problem, the concurrent multi-scale with manufacturing constraints mentioned in Section 3 optimization model labeled as CMsMC₁, the single macro-scale (tube's inner radius r_i) without considering manufacturing constraints optimization model labeled as MACs, and the single micro-scale (candidate material density $x_{i,j,c}$) with considering manufacturing constraints optimization model labeled as MICsMC, from the above three optimization models we can get the insight into how the interaction effecting of the structure and material, and the benefits of the concurrent multi-scale optimization.

In MACs model only the macro-scale composite tube's inner radius with the value range of $0 \leq r_{min} \leq r_i \leq 0.1m$ are considered as design variables and all the layers fiber winding angles are fixed at a constant angles $\theta_{i,j} = 14.6^\circ$ to ensure the same initial objective function in several optimization models. Here, r_{min} is the lower limit of the radius and we adopt $r_{min} = 0.1mm$, when the radius reach this limit, we reorganized that the tube can be deleted, $\theta_{i,j}$ is the fiber winding angle of the i 'th tube j 'th layer. In MICsMC optimization, with considering all the manufacturing constraints mentioned in Section 3, the fiber winding angles are considered as the design variables, r_i are fixed at a constant value i.e., $r_i = 0.025m$. The initial values of the micro-scale candidate artificial material density, $x_{i,j,c}$, may in principle be any set of numbers between 0 and 1 but in general the values should be chosen such that the initial weighting is uniform, i.e. $\omega_{i,j,c} = \omega_{i,j,k,k \neq c}$ for all c ; i ; $k = 1, 2 \dots N^{cand}$. In this way no candidate material is favored a priori. And with considering the DamTol constraint the initial surface values are $x_{i,1,c} = 0.33$, and other layers values are $x_{i,j \neq 1,c} = 0.25$. In concurrent multi-scale optimization models (CMsMC₁) the initial macro- and micro-scale design variables are similar with MACs and MICsMC, respectively.

6.1 Results

The comparison of the macro-scale optimized results, value of the objective and convergence of three different optimization models presents in Table 2. For MACs model, there does exist convergence problem. The iteration history is illustrated in Fig. 4. The values of objective functions C in Eq. (11b) are normalized with respect to the initial objective function $C(r_i, x_{i,j,c})^\circ$.

Fig. 4 Iteration history of the objective function

Table 2 Optimization results of ten bars composite frame structures

Models	Optimized macro	Objective	Convergence rate $H_{\varepsilon=0.95}$
CMsMC ₁		0.4491	100%
MACs		0.6759	100%
MICsMC		0.6637	No convergence problem

The detail of macro and micro-scale design variables optimized results are provided in Table 3-5. Table 3 presents the macro-scale optimized results of the tube's inner radius with the micro-scale variables fixing at $\theta_{i,j}=14.6^\circ$. Table 4 presents the micro-scale optimization results of the MICsMC model, the macro variables are fixed.

Table 3 The optimized tube's radius of MACs optimization model ($\theta_{i,j}=14.6^\circ$)

Beam number	1	2	3	4	5
Radius/m	0.0379	0.0356	0.0776	r_{min}	r_{min}
Beam number	6	7	8	9	10
Radius/m	r_{min}	0.0485	r_{min}	0.0507	r_{min}

Table 4 The detail optimization results of MICsMC model

Beam number	Optimized macro variables r_i/m	Fiber winding angle/ $^\circ$
1	0.025	(90/0/45/0/-45/0/-45/0/45/0)s
2	0.025	(90/0/-45/0/45/0/45/0/-45/0)s
3	0.025	(45/0/-45/0/-45/0/90/0/45/0)s
4	0.025	(45/0/-45/0/-45/0/45/0/90/0)s
5	0.025	(45/0/-45/0/-45/0/45/0/90/0)s
6	0.025	(90/0/45/0/45/0/-45/0/-45/0)s
7	0.025	(-45/0/90/0/-45/0/45/0/45/0)s
8	0.025	(90/0/45/0/45/0/-45/0/-45/0)s
9	0.025	(90/0/-45/0/45/0/-45/0/45/0)s
10	0.025	(90/0/-45/0/45/0/-45/0/45/0)s

Table 5 The detail optimization results of CMsMC₁ model

Beam number	Optimized macro variables r_i/m	Fiber winding angle/ $^\circ$
1	0.0381	(-45/0/45/0/90/0/-45/0/45/0)s

2	0.0356	(90/0/45/0/-45/0/-45/0/45/0)s
3	0.0766	(90/0/-45/0/45/0/45/0/-45/0)s
4	r_{min}	(45/0/45/0/90/0/-45/0/-45/0)s
5	r_{min}	(90/0/45/0/-45/0/-45/0/45/0)s
6	r_{min}	(90/0/45/0/-45/0/-45/0/45/0)s
7	0.0486	(-45/0/45/0/45/0/-45/0/90/0)s
8	0.0007	(90/0/45/0/-45/0/45/0/-45/0)s
9	0.0507	(45/0/-45/0/90/0/-45/0/45/0)s
10	r_{min}	(-45/0/45/0/90/0/45/0/-45/0)s

6.2 Discussion

The discussion of the results is done in the following.

- From the optimization iteration history of Fig. 4, with the same total material consumption, the objective function values of the four types of optimization models i.e., CMsMC₁, MACs, MICsMC with respect to the initial values decrease by 55.09%, 32.41% and 33.63%, respectively. We can intuitively observe that when the minimum compliance is recognized as the objective function, the objective function values of concurrent multi-scale optimization are significantly better than single-scale optimization, and the structure performance improvement approximately 23~28%. This reflects the benefits of the concurrent multi-scale optimization, and it's fairly reasonable, because, CMsMC₁ model can achieve the coupled effecting of the macro-structure topology with micro-material selection.
- Table. 5 shows that the optimized macro-structures based on the four optimization models, because MICsMC model only optimizes the micro-scale design variable, so it has a fixed macro configuration. The CMsMC₁ and MACs models almost have the same optimized macroscopic structure configuration that tubes 4, 5, 6 and 10 have reached the lower limit and the optimized macro configurations complies with the loading condition from the view of stress analysis of structural mechanics, except the little difference on the radius value and the eighth tube.
- Observed the micro-scale design variables from Tables 4 and 5, because the symmetry constraints is adopted in micro-scale design variables, so only top ten layers' fiber winding angles are listed. Fig. 5 gives the description of the manufacturing constraint on micro-scale design variables.

Fig. 5 Micro-scale fiber winding angle with manufacturing constraints

7 Conclusion

Concurrent multi-scale design optimization of composite frame structures using the so-called Discrete Material Optimization (DMO) approach with considering specific manufacturing constraints is presented in this paper. The capabilities of the proposed method are demonstrated on compliance minimization, subject to constraint on the composite structure volume. Furthermore, an extensive set of design guidelines referred to as manufacturing constraints representative of the actual industrial

requirements are introduced. These manufacturing constraints are explicitly in the optimization problem as series of linear inequalities and equalities and efficiently solved by SLP optimization algorithm with move limit strategy and semi-analytical sensitivity analysis method. These design guidelines have been developed that help the designer exploit the material's strengths while mitigating the adverse effects of the material's weaknesses which also reduce the risk of structure and material failure and the complexity of the design.

In future work, the concurrent multi-scale optimization of composite beam structure with variable cross-section, thickness and frequency optimization problem will be considered.

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